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Research Article

**ASSOCIATION OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS WITH
SMOKING AT TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL****Dr. Hamid Nawaz Ali Memon*¹, Dr. Zeeshan Ali ², Dr. Muhammed Khalid Shaikh³
Dr. Mashal Dad³, Dr. Sumera Bukhari ⁴ and Dr. Zulfiqar Ali Qutrio Baloch ⁵**¹General Practitioner Zulekha Hospital, Dubai United Arab Emirates²Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center Karachi³Department of Medicine, Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences (LUMHS)⁴St. Francis Medical Center, Trenton, New Jersey⁵Brandon Regional Hospital, Brandon, Florida, U.S.A**Abstract:****OBJECTIVE:** To determine the association of type 2 diabetes mellitus with smoking at tertiary care hospital.**PATIENTS AND METHODS:** This comparative cross sectional study of six months was conducted at tertiary care hospital at Hyderabad. The inclusion criteria of the study were fifty smokers of ≥ 35 years of age and either gender had history of smoking ≥ 5 years while fifty non cross sectional of same age group were also recruited as control group. The history was taken regarding the age for stating of cigarette smoking, number of cigarettes smoked per day, current smoking or ex-smoker and total duration of smoking. In known type 2 diabetic patients detailed history was taken regarding age at the time of diagnosis, medications used and whether the disease was controlled or not. Blood glucose was done in the pathology laboratory or by glucometer and other routine investigations were also carried out if required.**RESULTS:** During six months study total one hundred individuals (fifty smokers and fifty non smokers) were evaluated for diabetes mellitus. The mean age \pm SD for whole smoker and non smokers was 50.98 ± 7.86 and 48.84 ± 8.63 with male gender predominance. In smoker group the diabetes was detected in 34 (68%) patients while in non smokers the diabetes was identified in 12 (24%) individuals. The association is directly proportional to number of cigarette smoke and duration of smoking.**CONCLUSION:** The smoking is an independent risk factor for type 2 DM and observed in both the genders. The longer the duration of smoking, the more chances of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus.**KEYWORDS:** Smoking, Type 2 diabetes mellitus, Diabetes mellitus**Corresponding Author:****Dr. Hamid Nawaz Ali Memon,**

General Practitioner,

Zulekha Hospital,

Dubai United Arab Emirates.

Email: zulfiqar229@hotmail.com,

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus is a syndrome characterized by chronic hyperglycemia due to relative insulin deficiency, resistance or both. [1] It is a major health problem and is emerging as a pandemic. It is divided into type 1 and type 2 DM according to insulin secretion and resistance to insulin. [2,3] Recently cigarette smoking has been documented as an independent risk factor for type 2 DM. [4] Our study is based on this hypothesis, as smoking is the major risk factor for mortality and morbidity in developed countries.[5] In the USA it is estimated that more than 400,000 deaths result annually as a consequence of smoking. [6] Smoking is a major health problem in Pakistan responsible for heart and lung disease and major cause of mortality. [7] Current smoking leads to restricted daily life activities, bed ridden and disabilities due to chronic abuse and more institution and work absenteeism than non smokers.[8] Many of the deleterious health effects of active smoking have been associated with passive smoking.[9] In diabetic individuals, smoking increases the risk for both macro- and micro vascular disorders. Former literature raised the possibility that cigarette smoking is the risk factor for type 2 diabetes mellitus.[10] The reported relative risk for development of diabetes mellitus in smokers have 20-25 cigarettes per day ranged from 1.5 to 3.5 as compared to nonsmokers.[11] The risk directly proportional to increases in pack year history and number of cigarettes smoked per day. [12] Thus, this study was conducted to observe the association of type 2 diabetes mellitus with smoking at tertiary care hospital.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

This comparative cross sectional study of six months was conducted at tertiary care hospital at Hyderabad. The inclusion criteria of the study were fifty smokers of ≥ 35 years of age and either gender had history of

smoking ≥ 5 years while fifty non cross sectional of same age group were also recruited as control group. The informed consent was taken from every individual to participate in the study while the detail clinical history, examination and relevant investigations were advised. The exclusion criteria of the study were the patients with type I diabetes, secondary diabetes, on drugs that impairs blood glucose level like corticosteroids, thyroid hormones, nicotinic acid, ciclosporin and thiazide diuretic, the pregnant ladies and gestational diabetes. The history was taken regarding the age for stating of cigarette smoking, number of cigarettes smoked per day, current smoking or ex-smoker and total duration of smoking. In known type 2 diabetic patients detailed history was taken regarding age at the time of diagnosis, medications used and whether the disease was controlled or not. The subjects who were not known diabetic, blood glucose measured and diagnose diabetes mellitus according to WHO criteria and in this manner all the subjects were divided into two groups i.e. diabetics and non-diabetics and the association of DM was found regarding the status and severity of smoking. Blood glucose was done in the pathology laboratory or by glucometer and other routine investigations were also carried out if required. The data was saved on pre-designed proforma and analyzed in SPSS 16. The frequency and percentage was calculated and the mean \pm SD was computed for numerical variables.

RESULTS:

During six months study total one hundred individuals (fifty smokers and fifty non smokers) were evaluated for diabetes mellitus. The mean age \pm SD for whole smoker and non smokers was 50.98 ± 7.86 and 48.84 ± 8.63 with male gender predominance. The results of the study are presented in Table 01.

TABLE 01: THE AGE DISTRIBUTION OF SMOKER AND NON SMOKER POPULATION

AGE (years)	SMOKERS	NON-SMOKER	TOTAL
35-39	10	15	25
40-49	15	10	25
50-59	10	20	30
60+	15	05	20
Total	50	50	100

TABLE 02: THE GENDER DISTRIBUTION OF SMOKERS IN RELATION TO DIABETES MELLITUS

GENDER	DIABETES MELLITUS		
	Yes	No	Total
Male	23	12	35
	67.6%	75.0%	70.0%
Female	11	4	15
	32.4%	25.0%	30.0%
Total	34	16	50
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

TABLE 03: THE GENDER DISTRIBUTION OF NON SMOKERS IN RELATION TO DIABETES MELLITUS

GENDER	DIABETES MELLITUS		
	Yes	No	Total
Male	8	27	35
	66.7%	71.1%	70.0%
Female	4	11	15
	33.3%	28.9%	30.0%
Total	12	38	50
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

TABLE 4: THE SMOKING HABITS IN SMOKER POPULATION

NUMBER OF CIGARETTES SMOKED/DAY	TOTAL SMOKERS	DIABETES MELLITUS
≤10	22	12
>10	28	22
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DURATION OF SMOKING (Years)	TOTAL	DIABETES MELLITUS
5-10	15	10
11-19	30	17
20+	05	07
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SMOKING STATUS	TOTAL	DIABETES MELLITUS
Current	37	29
Past	13	05

DISCUSSION:

The study proved the hypothesis that smoking is a risk factor for type 2 DM and the later is more common in smokers as compared to nonsmokers. The limitations of the study are that it was performed on different patients suffering from some disease and it

actually did not show the incidence of smoking and type 2 diabetes mellitus in the general population. It depends a lot on history and many patients mainly females may not give proper history especially of their smoking habits. Several studies have been done to find association of smoking in the etiology of type

2 DM. [3-6] A study conducted in Japan, [16] men who smoked >20 cigarettes per day observed to be diabetic as compared to nonsmokers and the findings are consistent with the present study. The observation also previously reported by several studies [17, 18] and shown that type 2 diabetes mellitus was more common in smokers as compared to nonsmokers and directly proportional to the number of cigarettes smoked per day. A study conducted formerly contains 21,068 male healthy individuals and had history of cigarette smoking since >10 years, on follow up 770 new cases of type 2 diabetes mellitus were detected with dose dependent cigarette smoking.[19] In present study the male population was predominant, the observation also reported by former study, while the duration and number of cigarette smoking also consistent with the former literature. Another study recruited 114,247 female smokers free from diabetes and follow up for 12 years and 2333 subjects were found to be diabetic. [20]

In present study the diabetes was found to be more prevalent in current smokers as compared to Ex-smokers, the findings are consistent with the study by Shimokata H et al and Wannamethee SG, et al [21, 22] A greater public awareness is required for the hazards of smoking and people should be educated regarding benefits of quitting smoking. Media advertisement of tobacco products should be banned and not encouraged. Smoking at public places should be prohibited and banned. In the last every effort should be made to stop people smoking for the best future of their family and country.

CONCLUSION:

The smoking is an independent risk factor for type 2 DM and observed in both the genders. The longer the duration of smoking, the more chances of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus. Persons who smoke cigarettes for more than 20 years, increase number of cigarettes, or current smokers are at risk to develop type 2 diabetes mellitus.

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